

A Graph-based Architecture for Data Curation in Science Gateways

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Abstract—Science gateways can add value for researchers by empowering them to organize their data in a way that tells a compelling science story. In the DesignSafe cyberinfrastructure, users associate their data with metadata entities that represent different aspects of an experiment or simulation, then assemble those entities into a hierarchical tree which represents the overall research project. We present a novel design for a data curation architecture which provides feature parity with the DesignSafe model, but which can be provided “out of the box” in containerized science gateway solutions. This provides a path forward for advanced data curation features in gateways supporting any conceivable scientific domain. Our proposed architecture represents the data curation hierarchy as a directed tree which can be manipulated using standard graph analysis libraries. This design is broadly applicable because it provides a strong separation of concerns between the construction of the entity tree and the management of its constituent metadata records.

Index Terms—Science Gateways, Data Curation, Data Reuse, Software Architecture

I. INTRODUCTION

We define “data curation” broadly as the process by which scientists annotate data so that it can be understood in the context of a broader research question. Science gateways assist in this process by providing an intuitive interface to define and visualize the relationships between data sets. While an investigation is ongoing, science gateways give researchers a structured view of their project which can guide further data collection and analysis. After a project has been published, the curated structure promotes data reuse by ensuring that future users can understand the context in which the analysis was performed.

The DesignSafe cyberinfrastructure, maintained by the Web and Mobile Applications team at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC), provides a case study of a practicable data curation architecture. Using the DesignSafe gateway, researchers create projects that encompass experiments, simulations, or field research related to natural hazards such as earthquakes and hurricanes [1]. Within a project, users construct an inventory of metadata entities to curate data files. Examples of entities include inputs for simulations or sensors for experimental studies. Each entity has a set of files and

folders associated to it, along with descriptive metadata such as geolocation tags. After generating the inventory of entities for a project, users define hierarchical relationships between those entities. The relationships are visualized in the user interface as an editable tree. Entities can be placed within the tree subject to constraints; for example, an entity representing the output of a sensor must be a child of that sensor. When data curation is complete and the project is ready to be shared, users can initiate a publication process which creates a public view of the curation hierarchy and the files associated to each entity.

The DesignSafe data curation model has achieved a high level of adoption, with over 500 user-published projects and 40,000 download requests for data within those publications [2]. These metrics have convinced us that the hierarchical curation scheme provides a significant value-add to natural hazards research. We hope to replicate this success in gateways serving additional research communities. We are especially interested in implementing robust data curation within our Core gateway architecture. The Core is a containerized science gateway which supports file management and job submission on TACC resources via the Tapis API. It consists of a single code base which can be configured and deployed on-demand to serve any research group in need of a custom science gateway [3]. This level of flexibility poses a challenge when it comes to designing a data curation workflow, since it forbids us from making any assumptions about the specific scientific domain we might be supporting.

In this paper we provide a detailed description of how data curation is implemented in DesignSafe, and discuss why this implementation cannot be straightforwardly extended to additional research domains. We present an alternative architecture, currently in the proof-of-concept stage, which accomplishes the same goal of hierarchical data management but for which a domain-agnostic implementation is possible. We believe that this architecture will unlock advanced data curation capabilities in gateways supporting a variety of research fields. The key advancement is to abstract the curation hierarchy as a formal graph, then leverage graph analysis libraries to manage the insertion, deletion, and re-ordering of data entities.

Fig. 1. a) Implementation of the entity hierarchy in DesignSafe as a collection of metadata objects in which children point to their parents. b) Revised architecture in which the project root contains a representation of the full entity hierarchy.

II. DESIGNSAFE CURATION MODEL

In the DesignSafe curation model, a project is a hierarchical collection of entities, which are metadata objects that describe a selection of files or folders. The project itself is a top-level or “root” entity, under which are child entities representing experiments or simulations. These entities can have child entities of their own which correspond to experimental apparatus or simulation parameters. Entities are implemented as JSON records in MongoDB (accessed via the Tapis metadata service) containing descriptive metadata and references to associated files [4]. An entity’s JSON representation contains references to its parents in the hierarchy, but parents do not reference their children. The relationships between entities in an example project are shown schematically in **Figure 1a**. This choice of data structure has the advantage that insertion of new entities into the hierarchy is trivial. To add an entity, we just update its pointer to reference the new parent. However, without a well-defined entry point, it is inefficient to walk the tree for the purpose of visualizing it in a user interface. In practice, we circumvent the tree-walking problem by applying constraints; for instance, an entity of type “event” will always be a leaf node and will always have a parent of type “sensor”. Hard-coded constraints are suitable for a gateway like DesignSafe with a limited number of entity schemas, but they limit the extensibility of the curation model to a wider scope of scientific domains. The number of special cases to consider would quickly become unmanageable, requiring a new design approach which we present below.

III. REVISED ARCHITECTURE USING PROJECT GRAPHS

We propose an alternative architecture for data curation which retains the simplicity of implementation of DesignSafe’s parent pointer scheme but can be extended to gateways with an arbitrary or even user-defined set of entity schemas. The

relationships between entities in the revised architecture are shown schematically I in **Figure 1b**. In the new system, the top-level project entity is the sole source of truth for the entity hierarchy and contains a serialized representation of the project tree. The entities within the tree have no knowledge of the hierarchy, creating a separation of concerns between curation at the entity level (organizing and describing sets of files related to an experiment or simulation) and curation at the project level (structuring the relationships between entities to tell a compelling research story). Existing network analysis tools can then be used to explicitly model curation operations within projects as their isomorphic graph operations. Because most science gateways maintained at TACC are written in Python on the server side, this discussion will focus on proof-of-concept work using NetworkX.

NetworkX is a Python package originally written to support research at Los Alamos National Laboratory [5]. It provides methods to instantiate, analyze, and serialize graphs containing arbitrary data at their nodes and edges. In the hierarchical curation model, a project can be represented as a tree with edges connecting parent entities to their children. Our strategy is to use NetworkX to model these trees, offloading the complexity of implementing formal graph methods within the science gateway. The NetworkX model can be exported to a JSON-serializable format, allowing it to be stored in the database record for the project root. **Figure 2** shows an example of the exported tree for a toy project, alongside its corresponding graph representation. The metadata at the node level is purposefully minimal. Each node only stores an ordering index and an identifier for its corresponding entity. The purpose of the ordering index is to allow sorting of each entity’s children, for instance to order the events detected by a sensor by the time they were recorded. By storing only a few primitive values in each node, we can separate the management

Fig. 2. a) Example of a “dehydrated” JSON representation of a graph produced by NetworkX. b) Diagram of the graph produced by hydration of the JSON representation in a).

of the project graph from the management of its constituent entities. Users can curate their data within entities by tagging files and adding descriptive metadata, then curate the project itself by defining the relationships between entities. Because the serialized graph in the project root is the source of truth for entity relationships, tree-level curation can be accomplished without modifying the entities within the tree.

Fig. 3. Workflow showing insertion of a new entity into the project tree. NetworkX parses the JSON representation in the project’s database record to generate the entity tree in-memory, then operates on the tree using its internal graph functions. After the graph is modified, it is re-exported to JSON for serialization.

The workflow for operating on the project graph is shown in **Figure 3** for the case of a user adding a new entity to the tree. The entity hierarchy is contained in the project root as a JSON representation describing the linkages between nodes. To manipulate the tree, it is first “rehydrated” to its in-memory graph representation using NetworkX. This representation is a Python object with attached methods for manipulating nodes and edges. The node is then added by calling a method on the NetworkX representation which draws an edge between an existing node and the new entity. The in-memory graph now represents the correct state of the project tree based on the user’s request. Finally, the graph is “dehydrated” by re-serializing it to JSON and saving it within the database record at the project root. Future operations on the project tree will use this updated version of the graph as a starting point. While insertion of a leaf node is a fairly trivial example, this basic workflow can be applied to a number of more advanced graph operations. Once the graph has been rehydrated to its NetworkX representation, the server-side code has access to hundreds of graph manipulation and analysis functions. For example, an edge in the middle of a deeply nested hierarchy can be removed, then NetworkX built-ins can be used to efficiently walk the tree and remove any nodes which can no longer be reached from the project root. Metadata management is simplified, since operations which affect multiple entities can be performed with a single database transaction. **Table 1** provides a sketch of how several common operations on the project tree could be implemented as NetworkX graph operations.

Beyond simplifying the management of an entity tree, the revised architecture permits extension of DesignSafe’s curation model to gateways with arbitrary sets of entity schemas or even user-defined schemas. Our design places no restrictions on the shape of an entity besides that it must have a unique identifier. NetworkX requires no information about the scientific domain in order to analyze and update the project graph. If a science gateway needs to enforce restrictions on where entities can be associated in the hierarchy (e.g., a simulation cannot be a child of its own output) then these restrictions become configuration details and are not coupled to the implementation of the entity tree.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The DesignSafe data curation model, in which users organize projects by constructing a hierarchical tree of metadata entities, has empowered natural hazards researchers to communicate their science more clearly. In this paper we sketch a design for a curation architecture which provides feature parity, but which can be extended to science gateways serving more diverse domains of research. The new design accomplishes this by explicitly separating concerns between management of metadata entities and management of the graph containing those entities. Treating the entity graph as its own concern, we can leverage network analysis tools to simplify the task of parsing and updating the entity hierarchy. The next step for this work is to develop a full reference implementation

TABLE I
MAPPING OF DATA CURATION OPERATIONS TO NETWORKX GRAPH OPERATIONS

Curation Operation	Graph Operation
Create or update a metadata entity	No graph operation required. An entity can be stored anywhere as long as it has a unique identifier.
Associate an entity into the hierarchy	Hydrate the entity tree and add a new node with the entity's UUID as metadata. Construct an edge from the parent entity to this new node.
Disassociate an entity and remove it from the hierarchy.	Hydrate the entity tree and delete the edge connecting the selected entity to its parent. Use NetworkX to list nodes in the neighborhood of the project root and remove nodes which have been disconnected.
Change the ordering of an entity's children	Hydrate the entity tree and list the children of the selected entity. Update the "order" metadata on the child nodes to reflect the desired ordering.
Define a new type of entity to be associated into the hierarchy	No graph operation required. Implement a server-side endpoint to manage database records representing the entity, and update the curation interface to make the new entity type selectable.
Publish a project and its metadata	Hydrate the entity tree and perform a breadth-first traversal from the project root, ingesting each entity into a metadata repository (e.g. Fedora) as a child of its direct parent.

in Python using the NetworkX library. We will also investigate data curation in "serverless" science gateways such as Tapis-UI, which are implemented entirely in client-side JavaScript [6]. Because our design requires only primitive data types at the node level we anticipate that we can use Cytoscape.js, a client-side graph library, to similar effect [7].

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